

REGARDING THE INTERFACE, STRUCTURE AND SEARCH SYSTEM OF THE ELECTRONIC PLATFORM OF UZBEK-ENGLISH-RUSSIAN LINGUISTIC TERMS

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ABSTRACT This article talks about the principles of creating an electronic platform of Uzbek-English-Russian linguistic terms, the search system, the unique features of the panel window. At the same time, a complete description of the online dictionary, electronic dictionaries, and definitions of their differences and similarities have been given. The electronic platform and its advantages and conveniences for the user are presented on the basis of accurate information.

KEY WORDS: linguistic terms, dictionary, online dictionary, electronic dictionary, automatic dictionary, electronic platform, platform map, linguistic databases, html page.

INTRODUCTION

Before describing the interface, structure and search engine of a given language, it would be useful to study the achievements of world lexicography in this regard.

Electronic dictionaries are usually developed as a separate site. For this reason, the dictionary that we are creating a project should also be developed in web format. Naturally, there are also differences and specific approaches in the software and linguistic base of products developed in the form of a web format and an application. The electronic platform and dictionaries that take the form of the site must have a special interface.

- 1) Online dictionary - electronic dictionary placed on the Internet, which is widely used for various educational and didactic purposes. The online dictionary is mainly hosted by various search portals or search engines

(yandex.ru, rambler.ru, mail.ru). World Experience has three types of online dictionaries:

- 2) author's dictionaries fully compatible with paper versions;
- 3) pirated dictionaries obtained by scanning copyrighted paper dictionaries without observing copyright;
- 4) mixed versions based on copyright and pirate dictionaries¹.

Electronic dictionary - a type of dictionary that allows you to quickly find the right word, taking into account the morphological unit, phrase search, as well as the ability to change the direction of translation (for example, English-Russian or Russian-English). Their dictionary article will be organized as a database. Machine-readable dictionaries (Machine-readable dictionary) are used by computer programs to solve various problems (for example, processing natural language words). Machine readable dictionaries are a type of electronic dictionaries.

Electronic (automatic) dictionary - a dictionary in a special machine format that works as part of a computer program. Electronic versions of various dictionaries are widely available today. Unlike a traditional dictionary, an electronic dictionary can contain various media objects consisting of elements such as video, animation fragments, sound, music, in addition to text and graphic images..

According to the type of user, electronic dictionaries can be divided into two types:

- 1) automatic dictionaries for the user;
- 2) automatic dictionaries for word processing programs (information search thesaurus, frequency dictionary, classifier, morphological analysis dictionary; dictionary for machine translation).

Each zone contains a special type of vocabulary information: lemma, grammatical information or stylistic sign, meaning/comment fields. Electronic

¹ <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/%D0%9E%D0%BD%D0%BB%D0%B0%D0%B9%D0%BD-%D1%81%D0%BB%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B0%D1%80%D1%8C>

dictionaries have more fields than traditional paper dictionaries². An important feature of the electronic dictionary is its hypertext device. A link embedded in a word, phrase or image allows the user to select the text or image, immediately displaying relevant information/multimedia content on the screen³.

What is an electronic platform?

Platform (French plate-forme, plat – flat and forme – shape) – 1) high platform; 2) a smaller railway station; 3) an open freight car with a small board; 4) political II - a political program promoted by a particular party, group, social organization⁴.

Based on the above definitions, it can be said that an electronic dictionary is a dictionary whose data is automatically processed, stored on electronic media, able to receive data of unlimited size, able to automatically process requests and information, and working on the basis of software and linguistic support. An electronic platform can be called a search engine and a web site that can collect various electronic tools/software products for a specific purpose on one site (field).

What is an interface?

In addition to hardware, software is also important for computer operation. The interaction of these two tools that make up the computer system is called an interface. The interface is divided into several types: hardware interface; software interface; hardware-software interface. The hardware interface is provided by the computer device manufacturer. The balance between software and hardware is controlled by the operating system. In addition to hardware and software, a user also participates in making a computerized system work effectively. While working on a computer, the user interacts with both its hardware and software. The way a person interacts with a program, and the program interacts with a person, is called a user interface. Since the programs are different, their interface will also be different. The

² <https://studfile.net/preview/2532712/page:3/>

³ <https://studfile.net/preview/2532712/page:3/>

⁴ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Platforma>

user interface can be divided into several types according to its characteristics. Depending on the operating environment of the program, the program will have a non-graphical or graphical interface⁵.

MATERIALS/METHOD

Based on this definition, it can be said that the interface of the electronic platform creates the first impression for the user of this product. Therefore, it is desirable for the interface to be convenient, understandable, and simple in design. The interface of the electronic platform of Uzbek-English-Russian linguistic terms should represent its entire meaning and content. The interface should display the following information about the content of the electronic dictionary:

- 1) general information about the dictionary;
- 2) electronic platform map;
- 3) instructions for using the electronic platform;
- 4) dictionary of Uzbek-English-Russian terms;
- 5) search windows.

Enumerated are preliminary information about the dictionary.

Our studies of the interface of mono/multilingual dictionary platforms have shown that it is desirable to limit as much as possible distracting information or windows in the main interface (home page).

The first page (interface) of the online dictionary of linguistic terms of the Russian language provides general information about the electronic dictionary, in the left part there is a link to the dictionary in alphabetical order.

In the entry interface of the Glossary of English Linguistic Terms, the terms are arranged in alphabetical order by means of hyperlinks. At the top of the page there are general information about the electronic product, a history of the site, a glossary and a bibliography.

When these two electronic dictionaries were compared, the ease of use of the second dictionary was revealed. Clicking on a term displayed in the interface, formatted as a hyperlink, will open a new page and display the dictionary article.

⁵ <http://ask.ziyonet.uz/ru/question/1717>

The interface of the Cambridge Linguistics Dictionary is extremely complex due to its wide range of features: when the user enters the first page of the electronic dictionary, he is required to carefully study it first. The search field is also opened on the first page, and the result is also opened on the same page; in general, the result is always displayed on the main page, not on a new page. In our opinion, the interface of the glossary of English linguistic terms is convenient. It is appropriate to rely on this experience when designing the interface of the electronic platform of Uzbek-English-Russian linguistic terms..

RESULTS

Regarding the resources and structure of the electronic dictionary and platform. In the development of the linguistic database, the equivalent of English linguistic terms, their interpretation was based on the Oxford Dictionary of Linguistic Terms, traditional and online dictionaries of linguistic terms..

When choosing dictionary equivalents, the main issue is that the term is given exactly in the selected sources. First, a term from all language sources is selected and included in the list of equivalents. The explanation of each is not in the translation, but as the term is explained in that source (dictionary), then it is added to the line of comments. Uzbek-English-Russian linguistic terms are placed in one line for ease of use of the electronic dictionary: when a term is searched in one of the three languages, a row of terms in three languages is displayed one by one.

ANALYSIS

This will take the following form:

Glossary of terminology	Uzbek term and its explanation	English term and its explanation	Russian term and its explanation
ГИПОТАКСИС	ГИПОТАКСИС	HYPOTAXIS	ГИПОТАКСИС
ГАПЛОЛОГИЯ	ГАПЛОЛОГИЯ	HAPOLOGY	ГАПЛОЛОГИЯ
АФФИКСАЦИЯ	АФФИКСАЦИЯ	AFFIXATION	АФФИКСАЦИЯ

If a term in the first column is selected, a comment line will open for all of them. This view allows you to see the interpretation of the same term in three

languages in parallel. This allows you to learn the meanings of terms in several languages at the same time. The results window will look like this:

ГИПОТАКСИС	ГИПОТАКСИС	HYPOTAXIS	ГИПОТАКСИС
	(юн. – жойлашув). Қ. Тобе алоқали тузилма. Қиёс. Паратаксис	Subordination, especially of clauses and sentences. In the more general sense all subordinate clauses are hypotactic; in the stricter sense only subordinate clauses embedded in other constituents are hypotactic. E.g. in the stricter sense, relative clauses as in the definition which you accept and complement clauses as in	англ. hypotaxis, фр. hypotaxe, нем. Hypotaxe, исп. hipotaxis. Подчинение предложений; открытое выражение синтаксических отношений зависимости одного элемента от другого; противоп. паратаксис; ср. подчинение, русск. я надеюсь, что вы придете ⁷ .

⁷ https://classes.ru/grammar/174.Akhmanova/source/worddocuments/_7.htm

		realized that the game was up are instances of hypotaxis ⁶	
ГАПЛОЛОГИЯ	ГАПЛОЛОГИЯ	HAPLOLOGY	ГАПЛОЛОГИЯ
	(юн. оддий; тушунча, таълимот). Ясама сўзларда қатор келган бир хил ёки бир-бирига ўхшаш бўғинлардан бирининг тушиши: минералогия (минералогия ўрнига); қайна<қайнана<қайнона, қайни <қайнини<қайнини каби ⁸ .	The omission of sounds or syllables in a sequence of similar articulations, e.g. probably for probably, library for library. Haptics In semiotics, the study of touch as a means of communication. Hard Consonant A consonant pronounced without palatalization. In Russian there is a contrast between soft	(гаплогалия, гаплогалическое сокращение, слоговая диссимиляция, слоговое наложение)англ. haplology, фр. haplogie, нем. Haplogie, Silbenschichtung, Silbendissimilation, исп. haplogia. Выкидка одного из двух непосредственно следующих друг за другом одинаковых слогов вследствие диссимиляции, а

⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hypotaxis>

⁸ Ҳожиёв А. Лингвистик терминларнинг изоҳли луғати. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси, 2002. – 158 б. – Б. 29.

		(palatalized) and hard consonants. Hard Contact In clinical linguistics, a tense articulation producing strong contact between the tongue and some passive articulators ⁹ .	Русск. внамено-сец знаменоносец ¹⁰ ;
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DISCUSSION

Different words are used in the explanation of some terms. This is very evident in our Uzbek language source. The preface of the dictionary of linguistic terms of the Uzbek language says the following about such terms: "Some terms may be related to other term(s) by their content or some characteristic. Demonstrating such a relationship helps to clearly and easily understand the essence of the linguistic concept that these terms represent. In the dictionary, such a relationship of terms was indicated by special symbols. These are the following: (exactly), q. (see), comparison. (compare), opposite. (against)) . Since the explanation of the terms is taken from the sources, it is appropriate to quote them in their original form. One of these apples is a comparison. is pometa. In this case, the pometta is highlighted with a different color and placed in the form of a hyperlink; when the cursor is moved

⁹ <https://www.thoughtco.com/haplology-phonetics-term-4083268>

¹⁰ https://classes.ru/grammar/174.Akhmanova/source/worddocuments/_7.htm

next to this term (or, depending on the possibility, the word itself), the explanation of the proposed word for comparison will open. To do this, the program finds the original string of the hyperlinked word, selects the explanation of the word in the searched language and presents it in the form of an answer to this request.

Linguistic databases often contain a large number of annotated terms. Naturally, there is no limit to this situation in electronic products. But in order not to tire the user's eyes, not to distract his attention, a narrowing/expanding function is added to these comments. To do this, the length of the term annotation is automatically quantized. For example, an algorithm will be developed to add a function of expanding and re-narrowing to an annotation of more than 50 tokens. This function is automatically applied to all comments, that is, a comment with more than 50 tokens will take the following form. This expansion/contraction function can be continued 2-3-4 times. It depends on the size of the comment.

Working on the basis of such an approach is caused by the extreme size of some comments in S. Akhmanova's dictionary. For example, the term grammar in the dictionary is 2 HTML pages. Providing the explanation in such a way as it is given in a traditional dictionary makes it difficult for the user to accept the information. If you look at Figure 7, you can see that this online dictionary is formatted as an HTML page.

An optimal approach to this issue can be seen in the online dictionary of English linguistic terms: there is a convenient search box, when any word is entered in the search box, a result can be obtained. The result field is delimited from the search field, a short description is provided. If there are cases where the comment is long, the expand/collapse function is built in using the more... hyperlink icon.

CONCLUISON

An electronic dictionary is a dictionary that automatically processes data, is stored on electronic media, can accept unlimited data, can automatically process requests and information, and works on the basis of software and linguistic support. An

electronic platform is a search system that can collect various electronic tools and software products on one site for a specific purpose.

Hardware and software are required for computer operation. The interaction of these two tools that make up the computer system is called an interface. The interface of the electronic platform is the area that creates the first impression for the user of this product. Therefore, it is desirable for the interface to be convenient, understandable, and simple in design.

In the development of the interface of the electronic dictionary of Uzbek-English-Russian linguistic terms, it is necessary to follow the requirements of simplicity, comprehensibility, and aesthetic appeal.

Selection of sources in the formation of an electronic dictionary of Uzbek-English-Russian linguistic terms is the first stage. A. Hojiev's dictionary of linguistic terms for the Uzbek language dictionary, English language glossary of linguistic terms for the English language dictionary, S. Akhmanova's dictionary of linguistic terms for the Russian language dictionary serve as the basis - information bank.

The units of multilingual dictionaries in comparable languages are linguistically equivalent; partial equivalence; such types as false equivalence (inequivalence) are distinguished. Corresponding values of incomplete lexical parallels are called interlexes - international lexical-semantic variants of lexemes. If a word has at least one interlex in its semantic structure compared to the lexical equivalents of other languages, it is considered an international word: complete and incomplete lexical parallels are included in the international word.

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